

Details of Literature Explored for Unearthing Code Smells Research

Table 7: Mapping of literature texts with their abbreviations

Paper Name	Abbreviation
Guggulothu T. et al. ¹⁴	S1
Hejres S. et al. ²³	S2
Liu H. et al. ¹⁵	S3
Das A. K. et al. ⁶	S4
Shen L. et al. ²²	S5
Sharma T. et al. ²⁴	S6
Alazba A. et al. ²⁵	S7
Akhter N. et al. ²⁶	S8
Zhang Y. et al. ³¹	S9
Jain S. et al. ²⁷	S10
Jain S. et al. ²⁸	S11
Kaur A. et al. ¹⁹	S12
Dewangan S. et al. ³⁰	S13
Lin T. et al. ³²	S14
Gupta A. et al. ¹⁷	S15
Zakeri-Nasrabadi M. et al. ³³	S16
Yadav P. S. et al. ²⁹	S17
Mahalakshmi D. et al. ³⁴	S18
Grodzicka H. et al. ²⁰	S19
Guggulothu T. et al. ²¹	S20
Bouassida N. et al. ¹⁸	S21

Table 8: Code Smell classes explored in each of the explored research works

Code Smell	S21	S20	S19	S18	S17	S16	S15	S14	S13	S12	S11	S10	S9	S8	S7	S6	S5	S4	S3	S2	S1
Feature Envy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Long Method	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
God Class	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Data class	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Brain Class													<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
Brain Method													<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
Long Parameter list									<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						
Duplicated Code								<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>											<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
Large Class																			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
Spaghetti Code										<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>							
Functional Decomposition										<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>							
Primitive Obsession Detector																					
Misplaced Class																			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
Complex Method																<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					
Complex Conditional																<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					
Multifaceted Abstraction																<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					
Swiss Army Knife														<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>							
Switch Statements									<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						
Lazy Class																					
Speculative Generality																					
Refused Bequest																					
Contrived Complexity																					
Shotgun Surgery		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																			
Uncontrolled Side-effect		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																			
Message Chaining		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																			

Table 9: Machine Learning and Deep Learning techniques applied for each of the code smells explored

Machine Learning/Code Smell Class	Feature Envy	Long Method	God Class	Data class	Brain Class	Brain Method	Long Parameter list	Duplicated Code	Large Class	Spaghetti Code	Functional Decomposition	Primitive Obsession Detector	Misplaced Class	Complex Method	Complex Conditional	Multiplicated Abstraction	Swiss Army Knife	Switch Statements	Lazy Class	Speculative Generality	Refused Request	Controlled Complexity	Shedain Surgery	Uncontrolled Sideeffects
ADABOOST	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																							
ANNICNN	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																					
B-J48	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																				
CART	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																				
Decision Tree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
GP	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
Gradient Boosting Classifiers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																							
J48	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>														
JRip				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																				
KNN	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
LDA	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
LIBSVM	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>														
Linear Regression	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
MLP	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
Naive Bayes - Bernoulli	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
Naive Bayes - Gaussian	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
Naive Bayes - Multinomial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
Random Forest	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>														
RNN	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>															
Rulefit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																				
SGD	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																				
SVML LIN	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
SVML POLY	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
SVML RBF	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
SVML SIGMOID	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																	
XGBoost			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>																					